

Gibb's Paradox, Arrangements and Volume Issues

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Feb. 14, 2026

Traditionally, Maxwell-Boltzmann's statistical mechanics, i.e. $p(e_i) = \exp(-e_i/T) / \sum_i \exp(-e_i/T)$, is used to calculate Shannon's entropy $S(\text{Shannon}) = - \sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$. The problem is that this approach does not lead to additivity of entropy. In particular, if one has a box of size $2V$ with $2N$ particles (in equilibrium at temperature T) and partitions it in half (T, N, V) in each side, then $S_1+S_2 \neq S$ unless one adds a term $-N \ln(N)$ to Shannon's entropy. (This term appears in the Sackur-Tetrode equation.) $-N \ln(N) \approx \ln(1/N!)$, using Stirling's approximation and so it is traditionally argued that $N!$ is introduced due to the indistinguishability of particles and that this follows from quantum mechanics.

In (1), we argued that one may obtain an expression for S directly from the First Law of Thermodynamics, using $E=3/2 N kT$ and $PV=NkT$. If one wishes to have $S_1+S_2=S$, then one may add the term $-N \ln(N)$ to an expression for S to achieve this goal. Thus, one does not need to consider Shannon's entropy at all nor invoke particle indistinguishability. The key idea was that the extra factor $-N \ln(N)$ had to be added because of issues with the volume term, $N \ln(V)$ of entropy, and not indistinguishability of particles.

Here we suggest that the term $-N \ln(N)$ may be seen to enter in a natural manner which again does not invoke indistinguishability of particles and again is due to issues with the $N \ln(V)$ term of entropy. In particular, we note that one may obtain $p(e_i) = \exp(-e_i/T) / Z(T)$, where $1/Z(T)$ is a normalization factor using reaction balance. In such a case, entropy does not appear at all. Given this result, one may postulate a math function of $p(e_i)$ such that its maximization, subject to $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$, yields $p(e_i) = \exp(-e_i/T) / Z(T)$. The math function is $-\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$, (i.e. Shannon's entropy), but that does not mean that it automatically satisfies the First Law of Thermodynamics as well as $S_1+S_2 = S$. In (2), it is argued that Shannon's entropy yields: $S = 3/2 Nk \{1 + \ln(2 \cdot 3.14 m kT)\} + NkV$ which is not the Sackur-Tetrode expression. This entropy satisfies the First Law of Thermodynamics for constant N , but does not satisfy $S_1+S_2=S$.

If one considers $-p(\text{volume}) \ln(1/V)$ where $p(\text{volume})$ is dV/V , then for a single particle, this expression is $\ln(V)$ and for N particles, $N \ln(V)$ to be additive. Gibb's paradox arises because of this volume piece we argue because if one restricts N particles to a compartment of size V , and they have $E/2$ energy, then there is no issue with the partitioning of energy, but there is an issue with volume as the N particles are restricted to V in a compartment, while for the whole case all $2N$ particles may be found anywhere in $2V$. This is the crux of the Gibb's paradox, we argue and so one requires a solution to this volume created problem. One may resolve the issue by adding an extra function of N to entropy. If N is constant, this has no effect on the First Law of Entropy. This function is $-N \ln(N)$. If one wishes to consider energy changes due to N alone (T, V constant), then one may consider the Sackur-Tetrode equation for S/N and use $d(E/N) = 0 = -d/dN (\ln(N)) = 1/N \approx 0$.

Gibb's Paradox and Indistinguishable Particles

Traditionally, Shannon's entropy:

$$S \text{ (Shannon)} = - \sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)) \quad ((2))$$

$$\text{is used to calculate entropy, with } p(e_i) = \exp(-e_i/T) / Z(T) \quad ((3))$$

Here $1/Z(T)$ is the normalization constant. The entropy calculated in this manner, namely

$$S(\text{Shannon}) = \frac{3}{2} Nk \{1 + \ln(2 \cdot 3.14 m kT)\} + NkV \quad ((4))$$

(given in (2)) is not the Sackur-Tetrode result (3) because it is missing an $-N \ln(N)$ term. ((4)) satisfies the First Law of Thermodynamics for N constant, but not $S_1+S_2=S$, where $S_1=S_2$ for a $2V$ box with $2N$ particles divided into two equal V, T, N compartments. To resolve the problem and obtain the $-N \ln(N)$ factor, traditionally people have written $\ln(1/N!)$ and argued that this factor is needed due to indistinguishability of particles and that this condition ultimately follows from quantum mechanics.

In (1), we argued that one may obtain S without any statistical mechanical considerations. In such a case, one does not invoke indistinguishability of particles, but rather obtains S directly from

$$dE = TdS - P dV \text{ with } E = \frac{3}{2} N kT \text{ and } PV = NkT \quad ((5))$$

If N is constant, one may always add a function $g(N)$ to S such that $S_1+S_2 = S$. We showed that the problem which arises in enforcing $S_1+S_2=S$ is due to volume and that adding

$$g(N) = -N \ln(N) \quad ((6))$$

resolves the $S_1+S_2 = S$ problem. In particular:

$$\text{Volume piece of } S_1 + S_2 = 2 N \ln(V) \text{ while } S \text{ is linked with } 2N \ln(2V) \quad ((7))$$

There is an extra $2N \ln(2)$ associated with S which must be removed. This can be done by adding $-N \ln(N)$ to S . Then S_1+S_2 yields $-2N \ln(N)$ for this term, while S yields $-2N \ln(2N)$.

Again, we stress that the Gibb's paradox seems to arise because of volume issues and not particle indistinguishability. In particular, if one has N particles in V , then they are restricted to V . If these N particles are part of the $2N$ set in $2V$, then they are free to appear in $2V$. This, we argue, is where the whole issue arises. To see this more clearly, we propose to use a probabilistic view (statistical mechanics approach) to resolving Gibb's paradox.

Statistical Mechanical Approach

In (1), we did not use a statistical mechanical approach, but rather derived $S(V,T,N)$ through considerations of ((5)) alone. Here we use reaction balance to find $p(e_i)$, i.e.

$$e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l \text{ and } p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_k)p(e_l) \text{ so } p(e_i) = \exp(-e_i/T) / Z(T) \quad ((8))$$

At this point, the notion of entropy does not exist which is somewhat problematic given the First Law of Thermodynamics, which includes an entropy function.

We first ask: What math function of $p(e_i)$, when maximized with respect to $p(e_i)$ with constraints:

$$\text{Sum over } i \text{ } p(e_i) = 1 \text{ and Sum over } i \text{ } e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave} \quad ((9))$$

The math function in this case is:

$$- \text{Sum over } i \text{ } p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)) \text{ i.e. Shannon's entropy } ((10))$$

One may note that $p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$ is of the form of Stirling's approximation $\ln(n!) = n \ln(n)$ and suggest a physical arrangement scheme linked with ((10)).

We note that ((10)) does not include volume. If one wishes to follow the Shannon recipe, then $p(\text{volume})$ for a single particle is dV/V and:

$$-\text{Sum over } i \text{ } p(\text{volume}) \ln(p(\text{volume})) \rightarrow \ln(V) \quad ((11))$$

For N particles, one may suggest that it goes as $N \ln(V)$. If one calculates entropy linked to e_i along for ((10)), one finds

$$3/2 N \ln(T) \quad ((13))$$

As a result, separating a box of $2N$ particles with volume $2V$ in half (N, V, T) for each half, leads to:

$$3/2 N \ln(T) + 3/2 N \ln(T) = 3/2 (2N) \ln(T) \quad ((14))$$

There is no Gibbs' paradox associated with the energy part $p(e_i)$. The problem is the $p(\text{Volume})$ part because a partition in the $2V$ box means that each set of N particles is constrained to V and while for $2N$ particles in $2V$ with no partition, there is no volume constraint. This is why Gibbs' paradox arises. To fix it, one must counter the problem which arises due to the volume entropy piece. As already seen in (1), a solution is to add:

$$-N \ln(N) \text{ to entropy } ((15))$$

One does not need to invoke any notion of indistinguishability of particles or quantum mechanics.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that there is no need to justify the $-N \ln(N)$ term added to entropy in the Sackur-Tetrode equation in terms of particle indistinguishability which is often said to follow from quantum mechanics. In (1), we solved for S by using $dE = TdS - PdV$ with $E = 3/2 NkT$ and $PV = nkT$ and $S_1 + S_2 = S$ for S_1, S_2 representing equal compartments (N, V, T) in a box of $2N, 2V, T$. We found that it is the volume piece of entropy, i.e. $N \ln(V)$ which causes Gibb's paradox. Here we argue that this is because a partition on volume does affect energy distribution, but it does affect volume distribution. N particles constrained to V is very different from having these N particles being part of $2N$ particles which may be anywhere in $2V$. This is the root of the problem. To solve this problem, one may add $-N \ln(N)$ to the entropy expression. This does not affect the first law of thermodynamics if N is constant. If N changes and T, V are constant, one may consider equations for a single particle. Then, $E = 3/2 kT$ and the extra factor is $-\ln N$. $dE = 0$ and $-d \ln N = 1/N \approx 0$.

As a result, we argue that the Gibb's paradox is due to volume issues in $N \ln(V)$ because both N and V change when one adds a partition. One must then add a term to counter the volume problem and it does not seem that one needs to invoke indistinguishability of particles or quantum mechanics.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. The Gibbs Paradox and Its Relation To Work (preprint, zenodo, 2026)
2. Zhang, Z. Classical Resolution of the Gibbs paradox from the Equal Probability Principle: An Informational Perspective (2026)
<https://www.semanticscholar.org/reader/c9fce429b32acb191993147b5ebac6019941d7e2>
3. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sackur%E2%80%93Tetrode_equation